

Adaptive Multi-Sensor Waveform Design for RF Tomographic Sensors

Michael C. Wicks, Ph.D.[†]

Kevin M. Magde[&], William M. Moore^{*}, John D. Norgard, Ph.D.[‡]

Abstract – Distributed sensing systems incorporating RF tomography allow a trade-off between spatial and spectral diversity, however a large number of widely spaced sensors is conventionally thought to be required. A practical method of reducing the number of sensor nodes is introduced via the concept of the Virtual Tomographic Array. Furthermore, the geometry of this virtual array is electronically reconfigurable. Optimal resource allocation is accomplished instantaneously, with dynamic control based upon matching sensing modalities to site specific target and clutter observables.

1 INTRODUCTION

Distributed and layered sensing will offer the war fighter new technology for wide area surveillance that will render classically designed stand alone radio frequency (RF) sensor systems technically obsolete. Futuristic combat systems will be required to address intelligence, surveillance, and reconnaissance (ISR) needs from the troop level up to the theater level of engagement. Furthermore, the need to build a complete and fully integrated understanding of the threat environment worldwide demands that a myriad of potential threats be addressed simultaneously, even while the pursuit of aggressively hostile forces remains the focus. To this end, the state of the art in ISR technology is migrating towards net centric sensing (NCS) for net centric warfare (NCW). Recent rapid advances in software, computing, and networking, combined with high channel capacity communications technology, permits a variety of sensors to share data at the signal level as well as the detection level. As such, fielded RF sensor systems will be smaller and more affordable, yet designed to function coherently for signal level fusion such as afforded by coherent RF tomography.

Our goal is to develop a cost effective and extendable approach for providing sensing in a variety of applications in dynamically changing environments. As such, we foresee a new sensor archetype. In this paradigm, sensors and signals will be autonomously

altered depending on the environment. RF sensors will use the same returns to perform detection and discrimination processing. Sensors will automatically change waveform parameters to accomplish these goals. Disparate sensors share data and instructions in real-time via embedded communications. Intelligent sensor systems will operate within and between platforms such that the integration of multiple sensor data provides information needed to achieve dynamic goals. Intelligent sensor platforms working in partnership will increase information flow, minimize ambiguities, and dynamically change multi-sensor operations based upon an understanding of the changing environment. Concomitant with the current emphasis on more flexible defense structures, modern sensors will allow the incremental application of remote sensing assets by matching resources to the situation.

In order to explore the limitations of distributed and layered sensing, RF tomography for wide area surveillance is currently under development. As such, experimental data for demonstrating performance bounds as a function of signal bandwidth and multi-band signal separation are crucial. Performance is bounded on the lower end by non-coherent data fusion and on the upper end by fully coherent tomographic signal processing. These performance bounds are a function of sensor geometry as well as signal structure. Waveform diversity, when combined with geometric diversity, offers flexibility in sensor design and innovative alternatives that reduces the degrees of freedom essential in either domain to achieve desired detection performance. This technology forms the basis for the virtual tomographic array concept introduced in this paper.

2 BACKGROUND

In classical radar, frequency diversity offers one method to obtain additional information about threat targets. With the most basic form of frequency

[†] United States Air Force Research Laboratory, Sensors Directorate, 26 Electronic Parkway, Rome, NY, 13441-4514
e-mail: michael.wicks@rl.af.mil, tel.: (315) 330-2556, fax: (315) 330-1483.

[&] United States Air Force Research Laboratory, Sensors Directorate, 26 Electronic Parkway, Rome, NY, 13441-4514
e-mail: kevin.magde@rl.af.mil, tel.: (315) 330-3609, fax: (315) 330-2528.

^{*} United States Air Force Research Laboratory, Sensors Directorate, 2241 Avionics Circle, Wright-Patterson AFB OH, 45433-7303
e-mail: william.moore@wpafb.af.mil, tel.: (937) 904-9832, fax: (937) 656-4020.

[‡] United States Air Force Research Laboratory, Sensors Directorate, 26 Electronic Parkway, Rome, NY, 13441-4514
e-mail: john.norgard@rl.af.mil, tel.: (315) 330-2931, fax: (315) 330-2528.

diversity, namely increased bandwidth, high range resolution is afforded to the user. With high range resolution comes increased target-to-clutter ratio (assuming the target is not over-resolved), while target-to-noise is unavoidably reduced. Geometric diversity also offers the potential for increased resolution, and is a dual to frequency diversity (increased bandwidth) in classical monostatic radar. The extreme case of 360° of geometric diversity offers high resolution, even under the narrowband assumption. Operating with narrowband radar signals permits a substantial reduction in thermal noise power as well, further improving overall detection performance.

RF tomography leverages the spatial or geometric diversity of a multistatic radar to deliver high resolution moving target indication. RF tomography provides the resolution of conventional wideband radar, while using narrowband signals. These narrowband signals are particularly attractive with consideration to the ongoing erosion of spectrum. In RF tomography, some sites may have co-located transmitters and receivers, while other sites are receive only. By locating transmitters and receivers in a uniform manner, beneficial effects of geometric diversity are enhanced. Radar data is easily mapped onto a polar grid in the spatial Fourier domain. The location of transmitters, receivers, and frequency span of the signal (bandwidth), determines the mapping to Fourier space via the vector

$$\underline{V} = 4 \cdot \pi \cdot f / c \cdot \cos(B / 2) \cdot \underline{u}_B \quad (1)$$

where f is the frequency, c is the speed of light, B is the bistatic angle, and \underline{u}_B is the bistatic bisector unit vector [1]. Image formation is easily accomplished via Matched Filter Processing (MFP) in the Fourier domain, which has its origin in synthetic aperture radar (SAR) image reconstruction, and is considered a spatial frequency domain image reconstruction technique. This matched filter replicates the signal's expected delay and Doppler, via a generalized 'steering' vector used for correlation processing. The extension to moving target detection is not complicated. For each pixel, matched filters are applied for a wide range of hypothesized target velocities. In classical adaptive processing, a Doppler steering vector is used. In MFP, the Doppler steering vector is generalized to a velocity steering vector. The receive signal is the superposition of time delayed and Doppler shifted target signals plus noise. Each target has a velocity vector (speed and heading) that presents a unique Doppler shift in each transmit/receive pair. For MFP, a filter is computed for each scene pixel, as a function of time delay, and target velocity. To cover all pixels and target velocities, a bank of filters are employed. The MFP output is computed as a conjugate inner product of the received signals and the matched filter over all transmit and receiver pairs, in frequency and space. The received signal forms a data cube. The matched filter, for a particular scene pixel and target velocity, is also three dimensional. For multiple operating frequencies,

additional cubes would be formed. A single MFP output (pixel, velocity) is the inner product of these cubes. The process is repeated for all pixels and hypothesized target velocities. Threshold processing is then performed on each pixel.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Both wideband (1GHz of signal bandwidth) and narrowband (<1 kHz of signal bandwidth) experimental measurements at X-Band were conducted in an indoor test facility in AFRL in Rome NY [2]. Six cylindrical copper test targets were arranged within a 1 m^2 test zone as illustrated in Fig. 1a below. The geometry for the tomography experiment is also presented. The test targets are located in a central region surrounded by the measurement apparatus. Due to the static nature of the tests, sequential measurements using one movable receiver were conducted. All six test targets are clearly visible in the wideband image presented in Fig. 1b. Here, an X-Band signal with 1 GHz bandwidth was employed. In Fig. 1c, the signal bandwidth is reduced to 1 KHz. Three of the test targets are clearly visible, while three low signal-to-noise ratio test targets remain barely detectable. The green circles indicate scene calibration data. These measurements, collected sequentially using 60 transmitter locations and 480 receiver locations, clearly illustrate the imaging potential of narrowband tomographic radar using a single tone. Included is adaptive processing via the sample matrix inversion algorithm. This permits weak targets to be extracted from clutter and noise. Qualitative analysis indicates an improvement factor of 11 dB is achieved. In the next section, a multi-tone technique is used to reduce the number of transmitter and receiver sites to just three.

Figure 1a. Geometry of the six test targets for tomography experiments.

Figure. 1b. Wide band image of six test targets

Figure. 1c. Ultra narrow band image of six test targets and improvements via adaptive processing

4 A NEW CONCEPT: THE VIRTUAL TOMOGRAPHIC ARRAY

A tomographic system can be modeled as a spatial filter, and the factors that affect the spatial response of the system are the RF frequency and the position of the transmitters and receivers. Each RF measurement has a 1-to-1 mapping from the spatial domain to the spatial frequency domain, and the geometry of the tomographic system determines the shape of the spatial frequency response. Signal-to-noise ratio is influenced by the number of measurements used to form an image. The system designer of a distributed sensor for RF tomography is faced with the competing need of desiring a large number of transmit/receive nodes to provide favorable spatial frequency response and signal-to-noise ratio, and the practicality of using fewer numbers of nodes. If the nodes are fixed in

position the only method of altering the spatial sampling, and therefore the impulse response, is the constraining limitation of varying the RF frequency. The concept of a Virtual Tomographic Array (VTA) provides a solution to these issues. Consider an equilateral triangle with active sources located at the three vertices as illustrated in Fig 2. If one radiates identical tones of equal amplitude from each of the vertices, then the effective phase center is located at the centroid of the equilateral triangle. If one of the elements is amplitude weighted by zero, then the phase center of the array is located along the chord connecting the remaining two vertices. This phase center is located at the bisector of the chord if the two elements radiate equal amplitude signals. If the amplitudes are unequal, the phase center shifts along the chord towards the stronger amplitude source, away from the weaker amplitude source (see Fig. 2).

Figure. 2. Virtual array formed from three radiators using nine discrete frequencies.

Figure. 3. Effective phase center formed from two elements operating at the same frequency, with the amplitude of source 2 greater than source 3.

If the two radiating elements are spaced many wavelengths apart, then the array forms an interferometric pattern with the number of grating lobes equal to the electrical distance between the elements measured in half wavelengths. Modulating the phase of one element relative to the other causes a rotation of the interferometric pattern. The use of multiple tones, each uniquely associated with a phase center, allows the existence of potentially large numbers of phase centers. Fig. 3 shows a virtual array comprised of three transmit/receive elements and nine effective phase centers. The three elements transmit nine discrete frequencies with the weights shown in table 1. Three additional frequencies are required to incorporate the vertices of the equilateral triangle into the active sensor geometry. The support in the spatial Fourier domain, based on (1), is shown in Fig. 4.

	f_1	f_2	f_3	f_4	f_5	f_6	f_7	f_8	f_9
1	.75	.5	.25	.75	.5	.25	0	0	0
2	.25	.5	.75	0	0	0	.25	.5	.75
3	0	0	0	.25	.5	.75	.75	.5	.25

Table 1: Frequency Weights for the Radiators in Figure 3.

Figure 4. Fourier sampling associated Figure 3.

As the number of phase centers (and frequencies) are increased, the support in the Fourier domain dramatically increases. The array shown in Fig. 5 has a similar geometry with three radiators, however the number of frequencies used is increased such that there are 52 effective phase centers per side. The coverage in the spatial Fourier domain is apparent in Fig. 6, and the number of sample points is approximately equal to the square of the number of effective phase centers. This has a very favorable impact on the system impulse response and signal-to-noise ratio.

Figure 5. A virtual array formed from three radiators and 153 discrete frequencies.

Figure 6. Fourier sampling associated with Figure 5.

In the previous section on experimental results, an ultra narrow band signal was radiated in a tomographic sensor using 60 transmit/receive locations and 420

receive only locations to image complex targets in the field of view central to the tomographic sensor. However with 480 spatial degrees of freedom, a tomographic sensor would be impractical for fielding except in urban centers or areas of high military value. Using 480 ultra narrow band tones, and the three element sparse array defined above, we can create a number of phase centers which result in a VTA. The Fourier sampling of the resulting virtual array has excellent support in the fourier domain, and this is essential for detection and discrimination because of the impact on image quality. Reciprocity permits the three element VTA concept to be applied on receive as well, and is analyzed mathematically via analytic continuation. With as few as three elements, a multi-tone ultra-narrow band VTA can replicate the results achieved with an array containing 60 transmit/receive and 420 receive only elements.

5 CONCLUSION

In this paper the concept of the VTA is introduced. The use of common frequency tones between two spatially separated radiators form effective phase centers, and these collectively comprise a distributed system. This allows great flexibility in the design of the system geometry, and therefore system response. In contrast with physical radiators (which require deployment of hardware), the effective phase centers can be created, altered or removed quickly because the frequencies and weights that form effective phase centers can be dynamically allocated. Knowledge based techniques can be applied to chose optimum numbers and positions of effective phase centers. With current computing trends exhibiting exponential increases in processing capability, highly agile system configurations tailored to rapidly varying operational environments will become possible. In the absence of computing limitations, reconfiguration timescales would be on the order of microseconds. RF tomography using ultra narrowband waveforms is a method to trade-off bandwidth for spatial diversity. The extension to the concept of a VTA offers the reverse trade-off.

References

- [1] H. Li, et. al, "A Generalized Interpretation and Prediction in Microwave Imaging Involving Frequency and Angular Diversity," *Journal of Electromagnetic Waves and Applications*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 415-430, 1990.
- [2] Michael C. Wicks, et. al, "Ultra Narrow Band Adaptive Tomographic Radar", *IEEE CAMPSAP 2005, Puerto Vallarta, Mexico, 13-16 Dec 2005*.